

The Influence of Birth Room Spatial Qualities on Staff Behaviors and their Association with Women's Satisfaction Using Mixed Research Method

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ABSTRACT: Space Syntax (SS) is a research program investigating the relationship between human societies and space through the lens of a structural system theory. The growth in environment-behavior studies using SS in healthcare facility design has enhanced medical settings and the performance and well-being of healthcare providers. However, its impact in birth wards (BWs) and women's satisfaction is less known, especially in Saudi Arabia. Since most births occur in healthcare facilities, the configuration of the birth environment has become medicalized, supporting procedural practices that promote unnecessary interventions and hind women's control over birth. The SS uses various analyses to examine layout configurations providing spatial measures for spaces, which can predict staff behaviors, such as movement, patient visits, response time, and communication. This study answers three questions "how are labor/birth rooms (LBRs) integrated, visible, and connected to the ward system? What kind of staff behaviors do they promote? And does women's satisfaction with childbirth correlate to LBRs' spatial measures?". **METHOD:** A case study-mixed methods research was employed using SS analysis and a satisfaction questionnaire. The relationship between spatial measures and women's satisfaction was examined in three BWs in Saudi Arabia. One-way ANOVA was used to compare the women's satisfaction across hospitals, and nonparametric Kendall correlation coefficients were calculated to show the relationships between the spatial measures and satisfaction. **FINDINGS:** The research found that when women's rooms were visible, isolated, and at a shallow depth, they were more satisfied with their experiences. Significant reverse correlations between integration values with overall satisfaction, $p \leq .0001$, and satisfaction with LBR, $p \leq .0001$. Significant reverse correlations between step depths with satisfaction with services, $p \leq .0001$. Visibility value has a significant positive correlation with women's satisfaction with communication $p \leq .0001$. **CONCLUSION:** These findings propose that staff movement and room entries influenced women negatively, while fast response and communication had a positive influence.

KEYWORDS: Birth Rooms, Spatial Analysis, Space Syntax, Integration, Visibility, Step Depth, Women's Satisfaction, Healthcare and Facilities Design, Role of Research in Practice.

INTRODUCTION

Space Syntax (SS) research focuses on how human societies use space to organize themselves; understanding configured space itself, particularly its critical developmental processes and social meaning, is a related theme in SS research (Bafna 2003). According to the literature, there is a link between satisfaction with the childbirth experience and staff behavior and performance, as demonstrated by social and procedural practices (Setola et al. 2019). The most influential factors in the literature on women's satisfaction with childbirth experiences are the quality of provided care, type of care, staff visits, communication, and use of interventions (Altaweli and Bhiwapurkar 2022). These relationships, however, were not related to spatial measures or women's satisfaction. Using the SS theory and methods in other healthcare facilities, such as medical-surgical units (MSUs) and multi-bed wards, researchers discovered a link between staff behaviors like movement, entry into patient rooms, and communication and spatial configurations (Haq and Luo 2012). In MSUs, the integration value and connectivity value of public corridors positively correlate with staff and visitors' movement (Peponis, Zimring, and Choi 1990; Lu and Bozovic-Stamenovic 2009), while the mean depth of it negatively correlates with the speed of exploring spaces (Haq 1999).

Additionally, in MSUs, the visibility value of beds negatively correlates with staff movement (Seo, Choi, and Zimring 2011); integration value and visual connectivity positively correlate to staff entry to patient rooms (Hendrich et al. 2009; Heo et al. 2009); and accessibility and visibility values associate to staff communication (Trzpuć and Martin 2010; Joseph, Winkler, and Zamani 2017). Besides, the design of wards' configuration is associated with staff efficiency and patient satisfaction- the radial layout is found to be better than the double and single-corridor designs, and the double-corridor plan is better than the single-corridor design (Lu 2010; Lu and Zimring 2012). Visibility and integration of beds correlate with patients' feeling of security, depending on their privacy preferences (Alalouch and Aspinall 2007; Alalouch, Aspinall, and Smith 2009).

Applying measures found in studying other healthcare spaces on birth spaces may improve the healthcare providers' experiences and well-being. However, it may negatively impact women's childbirth experiences, as their preferences

and expectations during childbirth differ from those of a patient (Cheyne and Duff 2019). Many researchers called for the need to use the same methodology to examine birth spaces, considering the complexity of the birth space generated from their impact on multiple users simultaneously (Shah and Setola 2019). This study is the initial step in understanding how the spatial measures of the birth environment correlate to staff behaviors and women's satisfaction with childbirth. It examines three spatial values of LBRs: integration, step depth, and visibility, and analyzes how they relate to staff movement, entry to LBRs, and communication in three sites in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, and correlates the results to women's satisfaction.

1.0 METHOD

This paper is part of a more extensive deductively driven design of a CS-MMR that the ethical committees of the Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved at the University of Cincinnati, the Saudi ministry of health, and the three hospitals. The study includes qualitative interviews with mothers, a satisfaction questionnaire, and the SS analysis of the labor/birth wards. This paper only uses the SS analyses and the satisfaction questionnaire.

1.1. STUDY SETTING

This study examines the environment-behavior relationship at three representative labor/birth wards in hospitals in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Hospital A represents a standard of a government hospital type with 12 LBRs and offers free access to all nationals. Hospital B represents other government hospitals with 1 labor room and 7 birth rooms, and limited accessibility to citizens. Hospital C represents the private sector with 6 LBRs and offers paid services and a unique layout. In addition, the three hospitals are among the two highest birth rates in 2021 (Ministry of Health (MOH) 2021). The floor plans were collected from the management department of each hospital.

1.2. SPACE SYNTAX ANALYSES

This study uses the SS method to examine three spatial measurements of the LBRs: (1) integration value (i.e., the closeness of the LBR to all other spaces in the ward layout), (2) step depth value (i.e., number of steps depth needed to connect to LBRs from an origin point), and (3) visibility value (i.e., the visual connectivity of the LBRs from other spaces in the ward layout). The floor plan of each ward was redrawn in a simplified version using AutoCAD. The simplified floor plans were saved as DXF files containing walls and windows, while doors are excluded or left open for analysis. Then, each simplified drawing was imported separately into the SS's advanced DepthMapX software (Turner 2004; UCL Space Syntax 2022). The software was used to run the spatial analysis using "convex space", and "tile" as spatial units. The "convex space" was used for integration and step depth analysis and the "tile" used for the Visibility Graph Analysis (VGA). Each of these analyses generates numerical values, that can be extracted by hovering over a space, color-coded graphs, and table of spatial values. The visual graphs display the spatial values with a range of high and low values from warm (red) to cool (blue) colors. The numerical and visual data utilized the SS theory and the existing literature to compare the spatial values and their impact on staff behaviors.

1.3. EVALUATION OF SATISFACTION

Women were recruited using a snowballing technique that used a link and a barcode directed to the satisfaction questionnaire sent to women by healthcare providers practicing Doula and social media platforms to recruit women who had given birth within the previous three years at one of the three hospitals examined. 86 women completed the self-administered online questionnaire, 18 from hospital A, 20 from hospital B, and 48 from hospital C. All Saudi women had experienced vaginal childbirth in one of those wards. It was important for the sample to present one culture as the environment-behavior relationship highly influenced by the culture (Rapoport 2005). The questionnaire evaluates women's satisfaction with the childbirth experience. It collects demographic information, such as age, nationality, birth type, care type, level of education, employment status, and other factors. It evaluates satisfaction through four questions: (1) How do you rate your satisfaction with the overall childbirth experience? (2) What is your evaluation of the LBR? (3) What is your evaluation of the health services provided? and (4) What is your evaluation of the efficiency of communication with the staff? Using the 10-point Likert scale, 10 being very satisfied and 0 not satisfied. Using SPSS software, a coefficient at a 95% significance interval was used for both tests; One-way ANOVA was used to compare the women's satisfaction across hospitals, and a two-tailed nonparametric Kendall correlation was employed to show the relationships between women's satisfaction (i.e., overall satisfaction, satisfaction with the physical room, services provided, and communication) and the mean spatial measures for each hospital (i.e., mean integration, mean depth, mean visibility).

2.0 FINDINGS

The findings are presented in two parts: (1) SS analyses and their predicted impact on staff behaviors, and (2) the correlation between women's satisfaction and SS measures.

2.1. SS analyses and their predicted impact on staff behaviors

This part includes three subsections. Each subsection presents one spatial analysis, comparing the spatial measures for LBRs across the three hospitals and predicting their impact on staff behaviors based on the existing literature.

2.1.1. Integration of labor/birth rooms

Across the whole sample, the integration values of LBRs range between [~0.75 and ~1.84], with a total mean value of [~1.26] (see Table 1). The total mean of the spatial measures is taken as the ideal comparison value. The LBRs' mean integration for hospitals A and C are smaller than the total mean recorded at [~1.12] and [~0.87], respectively. In comparison, the LBRs' mean integration is higher than the total mean in hospital B at [~1.74]. That indicates that LBRs at hospital B are closely connected to all other spaces in the ward layout, compared to the rooms at hospitals A and C.

Table 3: Integration values of labor/birth rooms at hospitals A, B, and C. Source: (Author 2023)

Labor/birth room	Integration value		
	Hospital A	Hospital B	Hospital C
1	~1.16	~1.77	~0.75
2	~1.16	~1.77	~0.78
3	~1.16	~1.77	~1.11
4	~1.16	~1.84	~0.90
5	~1.16	~1.67	~0.86
6	~1.16	~1.67	~0.79
7	~1.1	~1.72	-
8	~1.1	Labor room ~1.74	-
9	~1.1	-	-
10	~1.1	-	-
11	~1.03	-	-
12	~1.03	-	-
Mean integration value	~1.12	~1.74	~0.87

The integration of the labor/birth wards' spaces is illustrated in Figure 1 in color-coded graphs. The (red) represents the "integration core" of the layout (i.e., the top 10% of most integrating spaces)- in this study, major corridors were the "integration core" in all hospitals. Rooms that have direct access to major corridors have a higher chance of being visited by staff than other rooms in spatial configuration. Figure 1 shows that all birth rooms in hospital B have direct access to the "integration core," and thus, the rooms are highly integrated into the system. The configuration of hospitals A and C have a median space between the nearby LBRs and the major corridors, which segregates the rooms from the system.

Figure 9: Color-coded graphs showing integration values of spaces within the birth/labor wards at hospitals A, B, and C, Source: (Author 2023)

The integration analysis shows that LBRs in government hospitals (i.e., hospitals A and B) in Jeddah have a lower integration value than the private hospital (i.e., hospital C). Hospitals A and B are standard double-corridor designs with/without a divider space to get to the LBRs. In contrast, hospital C is a radial design, mainly with a divider space to get to most of the LBRs. It seems that integration values of LBRs are higher in double-corridor designs with/without divider spaces. Hospital B layout, compared to hospitals A and C, is more likely to support staff movement as reported in the literature (Peponis, Zimring, and Choi 1990; Lu and Bozovic-Stamenovic 2009) while increasing the number of entries to LBRs (Hendrich et al. 2009).

2.1.2. Step depths of labor/birth rooms

Staff enter the labor/birth ward from the entry point (EP), physician's office, or nurse station (NS). This study examined the step depth to LBRs from the farthest point (i.e., EP) and the shortest point (i.e., NS). The total mean depth value of LBRs across the sample is [4.81] and [3.08] from the EP and the NS, respectively. The maximum depth from the EP was recorded at [8] steps and the minimum depth at [2] steps, while the maximum from the NS was at [4] steps and the minimum at [2] steps (Table 2).

Table 4: Step depth values of labor/birth rooms at hospitals A, B, and C/ two origin points: (EP) and (NS). Source: (Author 2023)

Labor/birth room	Hospital A		Hospital B		Hospital C	
	EP	NS	EP	NS	EP	NS
1	6	4	2	2	4	3
2	6	4	2	2	4	3
3	6	4	2	2	4	3
4	6	4	2	2	5	3
5	6	4	2	2	5	3
6	6	4	2	2	6	4
7	7	3	2	2	-	-
8	7	3	3	3	-	-
9	7	3	-	-	-	-
10	7	3	-	-	-	-
11	8	4	-	-	-	-
12	8	4	-	-	-	-
Mean step depth value	6.67	3.67	2.13	2.13	4.67	3.17

Taking the total mean depth as the value differentiates shallow system and deep system. Table 2 shows that hospital B's LBRs have a mean of [2.13] step depth from both origin points, which is lower than the total mean, indicating that the ward system is shallow at hospital B. At the same time, LBRs at hospital C have a mean value of [4.67] from the EP, which is also lower than the total mean, indicating a shallow system from the EP, while the ward system is deep from the NS with a mean value of [3.17]. In contrast, LBRs at hospital A have mean values higher than the total mean at [6.67] and [3.67] from the EP and the NS, respectively.

Figure 10: The step depth analysis and the justified graphs from two origin points (i.e., EP and NS) for hospitals A, B, and C. Source: (Author 2023)

Figure 2 represents the step depth of all hospitals in the form of a justified graph. Each vertical line represents a level of connection that is called "step depth." The (red) dots represent the LBRs, and the (black) dots represent the in-between spaces requiring a turn and direction change. At hospital B, all birth rooms have a secondary connection (i.e.,

[2] step depths), and the labor room has a tertiary connection (i.e., [3] step depths) from the two origin points (i.e., EP and NS). In other words, from both origin points, staff must pass two spaces to the birth rooms and three to the labor room, as shown in Figure 2. The NS at hospital A is [3] step depths connected to (4) LBRs and [4] step depths connected to (8) LBRs. At the same time, the EP is [4,5 and 6] step depths connected to (6,4 and 2) LBRs, respectively. Like hospital A and hospital C, LBRs have a tertiary connection and higher (i.e., [3 and 4] step depths) from the NS and [4, 5, and 6] step depths from the EP.

The step depth analysis shows that avoiding divider areas to LBRs and having direct access to one corridor decrease the step depth values creating a shallow system where it is easier to visit and explore all LBRs (e.g., hospital B). A shallow depth to the LBRs with low step depth values (e.g., hospital B) indicates less staff movement and more room visits (Lu and Bozovic-Stamenovic 2009; Haq 1999).

2.1.3. Visibility of labor/birth rooms

Visibility values in this study were taken from the approximate location of the beds in the LBRs, assuming doors are open. The total mean visibility value of bed locations is [284.6], with a maximum of [452] and a minimum of [216]. Table 3 shows hospitals B and C's LBRs have a mean value above the total mean recorded at [291.5] and [332.67], respectively. In comparison, LBRs at hospital A have a mean value of [229.83], which is below the total mean. This indicates that the layout of hospitals B and C provide better visual connections towards the women's birthing beds, compared to hospital A spatial configuration.

Table 5: Visibility values of labor/birth rooms at hospitals A, B, and C. Source: (Author 2023)

Labor/birth room	Visibility value		
	Hospital A	Hospital B	Hospital C
1	217	257	292
2	230	238	347
3	252	251	452
4	236	357	335
5	231	260	304
6	248	284	266
7	228	240	-
8	217	445	-
9	235	-	-
10	230	-	-
11	216	-	-
12	218	-	-
<i>Mean visibility value</i>	229.83	291.50	332.67

Figure 3 illustrates the color-coded visibility graph showing visibility distribution from high to low, ranging from warm (red) to dark (blue). Visibility means the visual connection and visual privacy of a space. Figure 3 shows that spaces with high visibility at hospitals A and B are scattered along corridors, while at hospital C the most visible areas are centered in the layout -right in front of the NS. LBRs at hospital C have the highest visibility value indicating better visual connections. Hospital B's labor room also has a high visibility value as it consists of multiple beds for women during their first stage of labor.

Figure 11: Color-coded graphs showing visibility values of spaces within the birth/labor wards at hospitals A, B, and C. Source: (Author 2023)

The visibility analysis shows that LBRs are more visible in a radial design compared to a double-corridor design. It also suggests that divider areas at the entry of the LBRs decrease the visual connection and increase the visual privacy of these rooms. High visibility values for the LBRs (e.g., hospitals C and B) could indicate more staff visits to LBRs (Hendrich et al. 2009; Heo et al. 2009). It also could support communication (Trzpuć and Martin 2010).

2.2. The correlation between women's satisfaction and SS measures

This part compares women's satisfaction across the three hospitals and its correlation to the spatial measures of the LBRs.

The women's satisfaction data from three hospitals are compared using one-way ANOVA. The results are presented for each of the satisfaction measures across the hospitals. A skewness measure was employed to test for the normality assumption of one-way ANOVA, which was between -.78 and -1.1. The skewness values between ±.5 are considered symmetric and normal. The values between ±1 might show moderate deviation from normality. The Levene Statistic to test for the homogeneity of variances showed that the variance for most of the dependent variables is normally distributed across the hospitals. The results are presented for each of the dependent variables.

Although there was no significant main effect of hospital type on the overall satisfaction, satisfaction with services provided, and satisfaction with communication, there was a significant main effect of hospital type on the satisfaction with LBR $F(2, 74) = 5.385, p \leq .01$. To find the differences between hospitals (simple effects), the Least Significant Difference (LSD) procedure was employed. The satisfaction with the LBR was higher in hospital C (M: 8.66, SD: 1.61) compared to hospital A (M: 7.22, SD: 2.81) and hospital B (M: 6.80, SD: 2.76) (see Figure 4).

Figure 12: The means of satisfaction measures across the hospitals. Source: (Author 2023)

Independent variables include integration value, step depth value (EP), step depth value (NS), and visibility value, and dependent variables include overall satisfaction with childbirth, satisfaction with LBR, satisfaction with services provided, and satisfaction with communication, are averaged across the three hospitals. Nonparametric Kendall correlation coefficients were calculated to show the relationships between the hospital's spatial measures and childbirth satisfaction. The nonparametric correlation method was used because of the small sample size and the deviation from the normality assumption (Table 4).

Table 6: Kendall's correlation coefficients between independent variables and the satisfaction measures. Source: (Author 2023)

Variables	Overall Satisfaction	Satisfaction with labor/birth room	Satisfaction with services provided	Satisfaction with communication
Integration value	-1.000**	-1.000**	.333	-.333
Step depth value (EP)	.333	.333	-1.000**	-.333
Step depth value (NS)	.333	.333	-1.000**	-.333
Visibility value	.333	.333	.333	1.000**

As Table 4 shows, there were significant reverse correlations between the integration value with overall childbirth satisfaction, represented in Kendall's τ coefficient; $\tau(3) = -1, p \leq .0001$, and the satisfaction with LBR, $\tau(3) = -1,$

$p \leq .0001$. It also shows significant reverse correlations between step depth from EP and NS with satisfaction with services provided, $\text{Tau}(3) = -1$, $p \leq .0001$. Visibility value has shown a significant positive correlation only with the women's satisfaction with communication $\text{Tau}(3) = 1$, $p \leq .0001$.

3.0 DISCUSSION

The results of this study highlight that women's satisfaction with childbirth is negatively correlated to spatial measures that increase staff movement (i.e., high integration and depth values). In contrast, it is positively related to some spatial measures that speed room visits (i.e., low depth value) and enhance communication (i.e., high bed visibility). Integration of LBRs was negatively associated with women's satisfaction with childbirth experiences and, more specifically, satisfaction with the LBR. Step depth value was negatively associated with women's satisfaction with services provided. The visibility value of the LBRs' beds positively correlates with women's satisfaction with staff communication.

In healthcare facility design studies, high integration values are associated with better staff movement (Peponis, Zimring, and Choi 1990) and more staff entry to patient rooms. (Hendrich et al. 2009; Heo et al. 2009) Since staff entry significantly influences women's satisfaction with childbirth, (Altaweli and Bhiwapurkar 2022) one would expect that a positive correlation would apply in the birth space. However, this study showed an opposite correlation: LBRs positively influence women's satisfaction when segregated from other areas in the labor/birth ward. The findings of this study indicate that the privacy laboring women need in developing countries (Srivastava et al. 2015) is not necessarily visual privacy - the segregation of the LBRs provides women with privacy in the form of control over the space, (Symon et al. 2008) having fewer people entering the room and having the ability to move around. The cultural preference to cover up could also contribute to why Saudi women reported higher satisfaction levels with the service when their room was segregated from other areas in the ward layout.

Mean depth was positively related to staff movement and negatively related to staff response time. (Haq 1999) According to this study, having a lot of staff movements in the room during labor and birth reduces women's satisfaction. While a quick response time by staff, which could be encouraged by the shallow depth of LBRs, was associated with higher satisfaction with the services provided.

Some researchers have found that visibility has some association with the level of communication with staff (Trzpuć and Martin 2010). This study confirms the relationship between the visibility of the labor/birth bed and women's satisfaction with the level of staff communication. The beds' visibility correlated with the patient's sense of security in other healthcare facilities (Alalouch and Aspinall 2007; Alalouch, Aspinall, and Smith 2009). This study also confirms this correlation in birth spaces in the Saudi culture as high visibility of the bed provides safety, and it seems to be prioritized over privacy during their childbirth experience when frequent visits seem to violate women's privacy.

The frequency of room visits influenced by high integration values was not desirable for birthing women, unlike the short response time of these visits that was encouraged by shorter depths (Haq 1999) from the EP and NS. Women's satisfaction with services correlates negatively with step depth- women are more satisfied when the LBRs are in shallow depths from EP and NS (i.e., lower step depths value), as the staff would move quickly, and response time will be shorter. Therefore, avoiding distribution areas of the LBR reduces the depth steps, thus increasing possible room visits and women's satisfaction, especially in a radial design. Therefore, a radial design without divided entries would increase women's satisfaction compared to a radial design with divided entries.

In healthcare design studies, the wards' double-corridor design was positively associated with staff efficiency and patient satisfaction. (Lu 2010; Lu and Zimring 2012) However, this study shows that, unlike patients who are in the hospital because they are unwell, the satisfaction of birthing women was positively correlated with the radial ward design with or without a divider entry area (e.g., as in hospital C).

CONCLUSION

This research is the first step toward better understanding the birth environment in isolation from other healthcare settings to improve childbirth experiences. It provided information on how the placement of LBRs within the layout of the maternity ward affects women's satisfaction, which can be used in renovation and new design. Since the environment-behavior relationship is heavily influenced by culture (Rapoport 2005), it is critical to design the birth environment to women's cultural preferences because they are the most impacted users from its physical setting (Altaweli and Bhiwapurkar 2022); thus, selecting three sites that share the same culture was critical.

Employing some spatial analyses that showed an influence on social behaviors in previous studies, such as integration, connectivity, and visibility analyses, helped identify staff behaviors at birth wards that may or may not be desirable by women at birth spaces. Therefore, this study examined the existing LBRs' spatial configuration and used the SS theory to synthesize staff behaviors while statistically correlating women's satisfaction with spatial measures. The spatial measures of LBRs influence staff movement, room visits, response time, and communication. However, these behaviors affect birthing women differently than other patients. The correlations between LBRs' spatial measures and women's satisfaction with childbirth showed that Saudi women preferred isolated LBRs closely connected to entrance and nurse stations with high bed visibility. Since culture can influence women's expectations of birth and preferences

for privacy and services, future research should include qualitative studies exploring women's preferences regarding staff behaviors, birth practices, and spatial settings.

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